

Awareness of Green HRM in Indian Organizations

Research Report

SUBMITTED BY:
ASHLEY GEORGE PGDMBDI2/2115
CHANDRIMA SWARNAKAR PGDMBDI2/2119
TRIYASHA MANNA PGDMBDI2/2171
MALLIKA PUJARI PGDMBDI2/2137

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ABSTRACT

Green HRM is a very new and upcoming aspect in the world of HR. Green HRM practices are now evolving rapidly because by taking into consideration the global requirements which may include the global warming, the recent period of Covid and many other environmental issues.

Earlier a success of an organization was strongly dependent on the ways of promotion, diversity in products. But nowadays the situation has turned, along with the above-mentioned points they still must work on to reduce the ecological footprints and give more importance to social and environmental factors along with economical and financial factors.

Many countries have already started working on these but with the whole pandemic situation many changes had to be made in the organization to make it more environment friendly and sustainable.

In this paper we made an attempt to study the present Green Human Resource Management practices and the awareness adopted by the organization and how are they implemented and their growth rate in Indian Organization scenario.

It also highlights the problems and factors that were faced earlier the pandemic and after the hit of the pandemic and how are they affecting the implementation of Green HRM in the Indian Organization.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

In the worldwide context, it appears that a significant number of firms adopt green human resource management techniques. Exploring and combining these green HRM techniques that are being used and will be used by businesses and other organizations will make a substantial academic and practical contribution to the HRM discipline.

"Green HRM" is defined as "the application of human resource management strategies to encourage the sustainable use of resources inside businesses and, more broadly, to promote environmental sustainability" (Mandip, 2012) Green HRM practices aren't just for businesses or corporations. Educational institutions may also make a significant contribution in this area.

Electronic documentation/E-filing, Online teaching materials, Examinations and result processing are all examples of typical green operations in educational institutions. Paper, folders, files, furniture, and other available resources should all be recycled and used twice, encourage carpooling to reduce commute. Early attendance, using laptops after a few minutes of sleep, etc.) are all ways to save power. After using the air conditioners, lights, and projectors, turn them off.

Replacing outdated and broken air conditioners and other power-hungry electrical devices its Video recruiting, for example, or the utilization of online and video interviews to reduce travel costs, are just a few examples. As an educational institution, it is critical to raise knowledge of this notion among employees and students. The college administration may address this as a policy issue, and awareness programmed for staff and students should be provided. Green HRM practices not only assist to keep our environment clean and green, but they also help us save money by reducing resource waste.

The goal of Green HRM in an organization is to

- Improve employee health and safety while also ensuring that all of the company's resources are environmentally sustainable.
- Organizing and motivating staff to participate in various procedures aimed at making the company more environmentally friendly.
- Employee training and development programmed that educate staff about green policies and assist producers in managing and reducing waste.
- Assisting the organization in reducing turnover and gaining a competitive advantage 1 opportunities.

A. Objectives

- To encourage the sustainable use of the resources withing the organization
- To develop a direct responsibility towards building a green workforce that recognizes, appreciates, and practices green initiative and supports its green objectives.
- To implement eco-friendly HR programmed that will result in increased productivity, reduced prices, improved employee engagement and retention.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

To explain the notion of green HRM, numerous research has been undertaken. Despite the fact that the literature includes a wide range of such research, this analysis will concentrate on five significant themes that appear throughout the literature.

Douglas Renwick, Tom Redman, Stuart Maguire (2008)

(Douglas Renwick, 2008) A review, a process model, and a research agenda are all included. Examines the growing need for environmental management to be integrated into human resource management. A number of reference frameworks for green human resource management have yet to materialize, according to the literature study. The classification of literature on the basis of the processes of entry to departure is used in this study to adopt a fresh and integrated perspective of literature in the management of green human resources. The role of green human resources in practical practices is also being emphasized, with the goal of gathering literature in the field of mapping and terrain in this area, as well as proposing new research projects in green human resource management.

Akshata Sakhawalkar and Anand Thadani (2012)

(Thadani, 2012) have studied current green HR practices and their responsiveness among I.T. industry employees in the Pune region. The purpose of this study is to verify employee awareness in Pune's IT firms and to assess the efficacy of green human resource management techniques that assist minimize employee carbon emissions. Electronic filing, cleaning sharing, conference trash, recycling, and training are all part of the research. Increase the number of offices and energy efficiency by using the Internet. Green human resources have aided in increasing operational efficiency, reducing, and eliminating waste, and renewing items and tools, all of which have resulted in higher efficiency and cheaper costs. These findings were obtained by the use of a questionnaire in this study.

Pooja Popli (2014)

(Popli, 2014) Green HR Practices, Its Awareness, and Implementation in the Industries in Nasik reveals that the notion of green human resource management is a new concept in the global environment, and it is having an influence on everyday activities on the environment, according to his study. This research was conducted to assist the researcher in determining if today's firms in Nasik have a climate conducive to green human resource management. The questionnaire was utilized in this study, and the results showed that most organizations in Nasik were aware of the idea of human resources management, but only a few were able to put it into practice.

Parida Ruchismita, Raj Shitij et al (2015)

(Parida Ruchismita, 2015) In their research 'Green HR: Analysis of sustainable practices integrated by IT businesses in India,' they discuss the different sustainable practices and policies included by IT firms and utilize E-questionnaires to gather data to measure employee understanding of sustainable practices in their company. Managers of human resources Respondents stated that Green HRM increased the company's profit share, and employees stated that it is a positive step toward energy conservation, that it is the need of the hour, and that it is critical for a sustainable future.

Mamin Ullah (2017)

(Ullah, 2017) Green human resource management is analyzed by means of its concepts, importance, practices, and implications. This research was based on a thorough examination of current or available papers in the subject **(Transfield, 2014)** Books, journals, e-papers, and websites are some of the additional data sources. As a result of this research, green human resource management plays a critical role in boosting resource efficiency and economy. It also aids in the reduction of waste, the improvement of work and living circumstances, the reduction of expenditures, and the improvement of worker performance and maintenance.

This course compared green human resource management approaches to standard human resource management practices.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to develop a trustworthy knowledge base of the GHRM field, a systematic review using an archival method is used. Our methodology entails categorizing and classifying the existing literature in EM and HRM (across the whole spectrum of HRM activities), based on papers published over a two-decade period (2008 until 2017). Only studies that provide empirical findings or establish theoretical explanations for the EM–HRM link are considered in this review. We don't publish studies that only give unsubstantiated advice on how organizations should or shouldn't grow GHRM. This study is based on a variety of GHRM practices that have been exposed in a variety of articles, including case studies, company reports, and survey results.

We also did a survey through a questionnaire that was published on our LinkedIn account where we did our research on focused group including people working in Indian Organizations only.

CHAPTER 4

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATIONS

3. Experience time period

24 responses

According to the graph the time period of people for working in any company was less then 5years i.e., 79.2% which was more. But also, the graph says there are people who have worked for more than 20years in a company their percentage rate is 12.5%. through this we can see that people retention depends on the work environment they get.

4. Are you aware about Green HRM(Human Resource Management) ?

24 responses

A. Our next question was how many people are aware about green HRM?

The answer for this question was mixed as you can see through the graph that 58.3% people are aware about green HRM. 25% people are not aware about the term green HRM and 16.7% of the people are not much aware about the same. As this term green HRM is new to everyone there is lack of awareness about the same to the people

5. Do you think the idea of Green HRM affects the organization's reputation ?

24 responses

The response to our next question was very positive as the idea of green HRM is very new and effective method to save the resources for the company as well to the environment. This can lead any organization to a better place and help them achieve miles hence the reputation of the organization will affect in a positive way. According to our response 75% of the people agree to the same. And 8.3% of the people do not agree. Were in there are responses were the option of maybe is considered as 50-50 the percentage is 16.7%.

6. Green HRM practices done in your organization

24 responses

According to the graph, there are organization who have started using the concept of green HRM through different ways as you can see through the graph activities such as car sharing, energy effective work space, recycling and CSR activities. The major importance is given to CSR activities that is 75% according to our response. 37.5% of people use car pool as their transport to save pollution. Next is the energy efficient work space were 62.5% of people contribute them self as green HR practices. There are organization who belief in the concept of recycle, reuse and reduce as looking at the response in the graph 62.5% have implied this concept in their organization.

8. According to you what does Green HRM consists of ?

24 responses

B. The next question for this survey was according to you what does green HRM consist of?

As green HRM by its name suggests for an eco-friendly environment, sustainable development growth, optimum use of resources and cost effective. So, according to this the responses for the same was 66% people think it consist of environment friendly HR initiatives. 25% people say by lower cost and better employee engagement. 20.8% people think it consist of preservation of knowledge capital and 54.2% say it consist of sustainable development goals.

C. Q If you have some other inputs for Green HRM, please share.

Lastly, we asked people to give some suggestion to take a step forward in Green HRM And the response was:

- It's all about an attitude and appropriate technology that are used for sustainable practices for ensuring greener future.
- HR dept will play a very vital role but other depts will also has to play certain roles. Include this in your presentation
- Simplifying processes and redundancies

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

Organizations have been found to be employing a number of Green HRM strategies in order to promote sustainability. However, a more serious approach to implementing them, communicating them to employees, and encouraging employees and other stakeholders to adhere to such green initiatives, as well as appropriately rewarding them, is required.

Furthermore, the green HRM strategy must be integrated into other HRM tasks, including as recruiting and selection, training and development, performance and pay management, and employee participation in green HR projects.

Employee involvement and participation, according to the study, would play a key role in promoting organizational sustainability by focusing on waste management, recycling, maintaining health and safety standards, implementing training modules, and promoting an environmentally friendly organizational culture. Organizations would indirectly increase the value of their brand by doing so, paving the way for a cleaner, safer, and more environmentally friendly working environment for employees and corporate stakeholders.

The overall analysis says that there is lack of awareness among people as well as organization towards Green HRM. People should initiative to known about it and update themselves and bring innovative ideas as this will be helpful in future run, Green HRM will be the future of tomorrow, as play a vital role to build the wellbeing of the organization.

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